

Impact of Relationship Marketing on Brand Loyalty with Reference to Nepalese Commercial Banks

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of relationship marketing on brand loyalty within Nepalese commercial banks, with a specific focus on Chitwan. Relationship marketing, which emerged in the 1980s, places importance on maintaining and strengthening existing customer relationships rather than acquiring new ones. It emphasises customer retention and mutual satisfaction, shifting from short-term transactions to long-term value creation. The primary objective of this study is to evaluate whether relationship marketing strategies employed by Nepalese commercial banks influence customer loyalty.

The research adopts a mixed-methods approach, utilising a survey research design with self-administered questionnaires. A sample size of 102 customers from various commercial banks in Chitwan is analysed. The findings indicate that Nabil Bank and Global IME Bank are the preferred choices among customers, displaying strong loyalty. A majority of customers prioritise deposit services, and a significant percentage engage in regular transactions with their chosen bank.

In terms of relationship marketing strategies, building trust emerges as the top preference among customers, followed by satisfaction, quality, and fast service. Factors that impact brand loyalty include customer satisfaction, trust, good relations, and service quality with affordable pricing.

The study concludes that relationship marketing significantly influences brand loyalty within Nepalese commercial banks in Chitwan. The establishment of strong customer relations and trust contributes to high levels of loyalty, particularly towards Nabil Bank and Global IME Bank. These findings highlight the importance of implementing effective relationship marketing strategies to enhance customer loyalty and competitiveness in the banking industry.

Keywords: bank strategy and trust, brand loyalty, commercial banks, relationship marketing